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Book Reviews

M. D. Joseph. *Adolescence and Personality Growth: A Philosophical and Psychological Probe*. Guwahati: Eastern Pub (India), 2021. 978-93-90434-41-1 pp. 66 Hdbd. Index. ₹ 495.

Adolescence is a developmental period that is remarked by substantial change in affective and incentive-seeking behaviour, which is relative to both childhood and adulthood, including a heightened emotional propensity to engage in risky behaviours and experience persistent negative and labile mood states. This volume on human life discusses the emotional and incentive-driven behavioural changes in the phase of adolescence, associated specially with rapid development and progress in physical and neural changes during this significant stage in the life of the teens. It throws light on what it means to be human, responsible and authentic. This book enables and encourages human life in this phase of life, helping the youngsters to move from childhood to adolescence from adolescence to adulthood and find one's unique and responsible place in the society.

With Forewords by Dr M. Angamuthu, IAS, Deputy Commissioner, Kamrup Metropolitan District, Guwahati and Most Rev John Moolachira, Archbishop of Guwahati, this book deals with the meaning of adolescence, the storms associated with it. It also takes into consideration the role emotion plays in the life of adolescence. It explores the role of friendship and leadership in this crucial phase of life. Then it takes up the philosophical notion of "I am that I am," which talks of personality, maturity behavior, moral growth, etc. the final chapter deals with the important role that the school and teachers play in the life of adolescents. The author, with a doctorate in philosophy, is a guide and mentor for adolescents, who can guide them in the path of morality, responsibility and wisdom.

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This book is gentle in its approach and open-minded in its vision and progressive in Weltanschauung. It is highly recommended to adolescents, parents and teachers and will be a good asset in all school and college libraries. It is a good guide to teens, adolescents, teachers and parents. **KP**

Nago, Santan FS. *In the Land of Jesus*. Rainbow Ad, Panbazar, Guwahati, 2020. Pp. 112. ₹ 300

The Holy Land today remains a goal of pilgrimage for all people, a place of prayer and penance, as was testified to it in antiquity by authors like St. Jerome. The more we turn our eyes and our hearts to the earthly Jerusalem, the more will our yearning be kindled for the heavenly Jerusalem, the true goal of every pilgrimage. This book is a picturesque introduction to the Holy Land.

Apart from buildings, the sea whose storms Jesus calmed, hill slopes on which he proposed the Beatitudes, the birds of the air and the lilies of the field that he referred to, make us feel that he is still with us, that he has just moved out for a while to return and enquire whether we have profited by the services he has rendered us. This colourful and illuminating book reminds us that the stones on which Jesus walked are still charged with his memory and continue to “cry out” the Good News. Because of this, the Synod fathers recalled the felicitous phrase that speaks of the Holy Land as “the Fifth Gospel, not written on ink but written in stones.”

This book inspires us to stand on the very place where Jesus lived; seeing the same sights he saw; walking the steps he walked; listening to him at the places he preached and created miracles; bowing at the spot he was born; kneeling at Calvary where he died; and worshipping him at the tomb he was buried and resurrected from. This creates a profound sense of union with Jesus.

The book is meaningfully divided into seven sections like “From Nazareth to River Jordan,” and “Jerusalem Panorama.” Stations of the Cross (pp. 61 ff) and the Via Dolorosa (p. 60) are remarkably poignant. The concise and clear headings and notes make this book, printed on glossy paper, a prize worth possessing. The author urges us, “As pilgrims on this earth, let us enter the land of Jesus from the very place where it all began” (p. 11). It is recommended to all Christians, especially to those who cannot afford travel or pilgrimage to the Holy Land. **KP**

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